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Application

GB2613968.3

Application details

Application number	GB2613968.3
Application title	M.A.R.S. Companion: System and Method for Emotional Architecture and Empathetic Interaction in AI Companions
Status	Filed

Dates

Lodged date	17 June 2026
Filing date	17 June 2026

Applicants

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